

**MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN THE HYPOTHALAMIC-
PITUITARY NEUROSECRETORY SYSTEM DURING AEROBIC
EXERCISE**

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Currently, the development of sports around the world requires in-depth study of the reactivity of the body depending on the degree of load and duration of training [1, 3]. We know that any load on the body is realized against the background of the predominance of activity of the sympathoadrenal system [10,13]. Such activation contributes to the realization of ergotropic activity in the body of the athlete, depending on the type of load. Against the background of this kind of activation, the activity of the endocrine system is realized to ensure the realization of the humoral regulation of adaptive processes in the body [11,5,6,13] with current stress with activation of adrenal hormones (glucocorticoids, mineralocorticoids, catecholamines, respectively, and long-term periods of adaptation and anabolic adrenal hormones) [7,8]. In addition, an increase in the synthesis and secretion of hormones was revealed thyroid gland, pancreas and hormones of the reproductive gland. But the works devoted to the reactivity of SON, hypothalamus PVN at the present time during physical exertion have not been studied enough and remain an urgent problem.

The purpose of the study. He will study the reactivity of the hypothalamic-pituitary neurosecretory system during aerobic exercise with swimming.

The object of the investigation. The experiment was carried out on 40 white non-native male rats with a weight of 130-220 grams. In whom forced physical exertion was performed according to the method of Karkishchenko N.N., Karkishchenko V.N. (2017), and the morphofunctional reaction of the neurosecretory cells (NSC)

of the supraoptic nucleus (SON) and the paraventricular nucleus (PVN) of the hypothalamus after exertion was studied through 1,-7,-14,-21,-30, days and 2 and 3 months of exercise with swimming.

The data obtained and their discussion. With aerobic exercise in rats with chronic swimming in water with 7.5% load from day 1 to day 21, the load in the SON and PVN of the hypothalamus increased the number of NSC with high functional activity 3.6 ($P<0.001$) times, the nuclear cytoplasmic index 1.13 times ($P<0.001$) an increase in the area of glial cell nuclei 1.3 A protective reaction was formed three times ($P<0.001$) compared with intact animals.

Starting from day 21 to 3 months of exercise against the background of hyperhydration of the nuclei of the NSC, an increase in the number of glial cells, and the area of their nuclei, an increase in the content of neurosecretory substances (NSV) in the NSC compared to the days before the running load in the SON and PVN hypothalamus, an adaptive reaction to the rotation of the current kind of physical activity with swimming was observed

If we interpret the data with the data of scientists, the increase in the number of glial cells and the surface area of the nucleus, as well as the hyperhydration of the nuclei of the NSC, revealed by us by the 21st day of the load, indicates the provision of protective trophic processes for a kind of swimming [2,4,5,6,9,14,15].

Based on the data obtained, the following conclusion can be drawn.

1. During aerobic exercise with swimming up to 21 days of exercise, an increase in the reactivity of SON, hypothalamus, and an adaptive reaction to swimming were found against the background of an increase in the reactivity of SON.
2. Starting from 21 days to 3 months of exercise, against the background of hyperhydration of the nuclei of NSC SON and PVN, and an increase in the number and area of glial cell nuclei with an increase in the number of NSV in the NSC, the adaptation of the animal body to swimming is ensured.

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